

Wet bubble: identification, prevention and effective management

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The problem

Wet bubble, caused by the fungal pathogen *Mycogone pernicioso*, reduces productivity of mushroom crops. Its spores are dispersed through vectors (flies and mites).

The solution

Growers can treat wet bubble with phytosanitary products, based on *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*. Correct management and sanitation remain the only preventive measures.

Benefits

Preventive measures can reduce economic losses due low production and costs of phytosanitary products.

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Practical recommendations

Identify disease outbreaks early: visit the crop regularly with a flashlight to check the casing.

(1) Recommendations on specific measures to apply once the disease has appeared:

- Remove large bubbles using hand protection.
- Cover with salt affected mushrooms and holes from bubble removal.
- Avoid excessively wet casing soil and irrigating the bubbles (that would disperse spores).
- Avoid touching the bubbles. If you do, change your gloves immediately.
- As a harvester, disinfect your hands with hand sanitizer before and after putting on gloves.

(2) Recommendations to prevent appearance:

Maintenance:

- Disinfect your work tools before and after use.
- Work from the most recent to the oldest crop.
- Discard leftover casing material from previous crops.
- Store casing containers in a clean area to prevent contamination.

Vectors:

- Use air filters to prevent vector entrance.
- Use black lights in the gates and plastic treated with insecticide/paraffin oil.
- Use adhesive plates with pheromones.

About BIOSCHAMP and this Practice Abstract

This practice abstract was elaborated in the BIOSCHAMP project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format. © 2024

Project dates: from October 2020 to September 2024.

Goal: develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges, improving the mushroom sector industrial profitability while reducing the agronomical need for pesticides by 90 %.